

The Impact of Swift Electrons on the Segregation of Ni-Au Nanoalloys

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We report on the electron beam-induced segregation of alloyed Ni-Au clusters into a Ni and a Au rich phase at temperatures above the miscibility gap of the binary system. The nanoparticles, with diameters of less than 10 nm, are grown fully inert in superfluid helium droplets with a Ni-Au core-shell morphology. Upon heating, the clusters are alloyed and subsequently transformed to a Janus-type morphology under irradiation with swift electrons. The underlying mechanisms are studied experimentally via *in situ* scanning transmission electron microscopy and theoretically via atomistic simulation techniques under consideration of elastic electron interactions. We find that the segregation kinetics is highly temperature-dependent and attribute this behaviour to diffusive relaxation processes. The presented results shed light on radiation induced phenomena using clusters as model system and suggest new routes for the synthesis of structures in non-equilibrium configurations.

The effect of charged particle irradiation on solids is of high interest for a large number of fields ranging from reactor material research¹ and experimental particle physics² to medicine³, semiconductor physics⁴ and nano material characterization⁵. Ion and electron irradiation leads to defect formation and alters material properties. These effects become especially apparent in nanostructured materials due to their high amount of low-coordinated and thus weakly bound surface or interface atoms^{6,7}.

Although these processes are often unwanted, they give rise to some interesting phenomena, which can also be harnessed for material modifications. For instance, the electron beam-induced fabrication of metallic nanostructures⁸, the formation of crystalline Si nanodots in a SiO₂ film⁹ and the creation of hollow and toroidal NiO particles¹⁰ were reported. In this context, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) is a valuable tool to study irradiation effects *in situ* on an atomic scale under controlled conditions. STEM has also been used to study defect generation and impurity diffusion in 2D materials^{11–13}, adatom movement^{14,15} as well as cluster sintering¹⁶.

In the present work, we report on the electron beam-induced segregation of alloyed Ni-Au clusters into a Ni rich and a Au rich part, at elevated temperatures.

Despite the relatively simple phase diagram of the Ni-Au system (see Supplementary Material) it exhibits highly interesting thermodynamic properties, which have been studied in the bulk^{17–20}. However, very little is known about the behavior of the system in nano-scaled, surface-dominated morphologies. Both Ni and Au crystallize in a face-centred crystal structure with a lattice mismatch of approximately 15% ($a_{\text{Ni}}=3.524 \text{ \AA}$ to $a_{\text{Au}}=4.079 \text{ \AA}$)²¹. This difference results in a positive contribution to the mixing enthalpy and thus leads to a miscibility

gap in the phase diagram at lower temperatures over the full concentration range. The difference in electronegativity between Ni (1.91) and Au (2.4)²¹, in contrast, contributes negatively to the mixing enthalpy. These two enthalpy terms of opposite sign result in phase separation on the long range at lower temperatures and short range ordering at higher temperatures¹⁹. In the bulk the competition between short-range ordering and long-range phase separation leads to spinodal decomposition. Periodic concentration variations are formed when a homogenized and quenched Au-rich crystal is annealed within the miscibility gap^{20,22}. However, we observe electron beam-induced segregation at temperatures above the miscibility gap, which cannot be understood within thermodynamic equilibrium. Compared to previous work on thin films, formation of modulated structures was not observed²³.

Our experiments are performed on a probe-corrected FEI Titan³ G2 60-300 microscope, equipped with a Fischione HAADF (High-angle annular dark-field) detector (Model 3000). Furthermore, a Gatan Quantum energy filter for electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) is attached to the microscope. Clusters were transferred from the synthesis facility to the microscope in an evacuated vessel, reducing the exposure time to environmental conditions to 10 min at maximum. The microscope was operated at 300 keV in STEM mode and the beam current was set to 80 pA, which is a typical value for standard STEM experiments. *In situ* heating experiments were performed with a DENSsolutions Wildfire D5 holder using DENSsolutions Nano-Chip XT carbon heating chips with a 5 nm amorphous carbon film.

The Ni-Au core-shell clusters are synthesised with the helium droplet technique²⁴. This method allows the synthesis of clusters with high purity, under ultra-high vacuum conditions, without the use of surfactants. Pressurized (20 bar) He gas, with a purity of 99.9999%, is expanded through a 5 μm nozzle into vacuum. The temperature of the nozzle is set to 7 K, which leads to a mean droplet size of $\sim 10^7$ He atoms²⁵. The resulting droplet beam enters a pick-up chamber ($\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar) and sequentially crosses two

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FIG. 1. STEM HAADF images of different Ni-Au core-shell clusters in their initial, as deposited state, exhibiting a variety of morphologies

resistively-heated pick-up cells. Evaporated atoms are captured by the helium droplets, where they start to agglomerate to clusters. Finally, the droplet beam is terminated by the heatable chip, where the remaining He evaporates, leaving the clusters on the carbon surface.

Cluster morphologies are determined by the sequence of the pick-up cells and the size of the He droplets. The composition was set to 30 at% Ni and 70 at% Au on average. For details on the experimental setup the reader is referred to Ref. 24,26.

The acquired STEM time-series can easily contain several hundred images, which makes the use of automatic image processing routines inevitable. To calculate the number of electrons applied to the particles we extracted information about the projected area image by image with a script written in MathWorks Inc. Matlab (version R2017b). To this end, each image was convoluted with a 5x5 pixel averaging filter to reduce the influence of noise and intensity variations by atomic columns. For automatic particle detection each image pixel was classified using an expectation-maximisation clustering algorithm based on a Gaussian mixture model²⁷. Image pixels that were assigned to the cluster area were then used to calculate an integrated HAADF intensity value. The background intensity was subtracted by using the mean value of the remaining pixels.

In our experiments the clusters initially exhibit a Ni-Au core-shell morphology, given by the sequence of He-droplet doping in the synthesis facility. The shape of the clusters varies between spherical for smaller clusters to more elongated for larger clusters, as shown in the STEM HAADF images in Figure 1. The reason for the elongation is the occurrence of quantum vortices inside the superfluid He droplets, guiding particle growth along these vortices^{28,29}. The strong Z-dependency of the HAADF contrast allows to distinguish clearly between the dark Ni core and the bright Au shell. Single Au atoms can also be identified on the adjacent carbon substrate. The presence of a closed Au layer effectively prevents beam-induced oxidation at room temperature. Such oxidation effects have been reported previously for pure Ni clusters¹⁰ as well as for Ni-Au clusters with an incomplete Au shell³⁰. At temperatures above $\sim 150^\circ\text{C}$ oxidative adsorbents (such as water) evaporate and oxidation stops. The absence of oxygen in the cluster is verified by EELS (see Supplementary Material).

Upon heating above $\sim 400^\circ\text{C}$ the clusters start to form an alloy. Alloyed clusters retain their morphology after cooling down to room temperature. Despite being the energetically

FIG. 2. (a) STEM HAADF image series showing the beam-induced phase separation of an initially alloyed Ni-Au cluster at 600°C ; Orange arrows mark the stable Ni rich inclusion in the Au phase. A Green arrow in the last image marks a stable Au layer on the Ni surface; the inset shows an enlarged image of the region. (dwell time: $2.4\ \mu\text{s}$, probe current: $80\ \text{pA}$, electrons deposited on the cluster area per image: $\sim 5.6 \times 10^7$ electrons), scale bar corresponds to 2 nm (Multimedia View). (b) Projected area values and the corresponding integrated intensity values of the cluster from the image series in (a) as a function of the total number of electrons applied on the cluster

preferable configuration above 400°C , we see that electron beam irradiation triggers the segregation of the alloy into a Ni rich and a Au rich phase.

The process is illustrated in Figure 2a, showing the evolution of one initially alloyed cluster at a constant temperature of 600°C at six different stages. These images are extracted from a time-series consisting of 204 STEM HAADF images with a resolution of 512×512 pixel. At the beginning the cluster is alloyed. Ni concentration variations, however, cause several darker features in the HAADF images. Notably, a spherical Ni core with a diameter of ~ 1 nm remains in the particle centre, marked with an orange arrow, and retains its size and shape over the full image series. A remaining core of similar size is observed in most clusters upon heating in our experiments. The remarkable stability of this small residual core in the cluster centre has also been reported theoretically for similar systems³¹ and is attributed to a decreased formation enthalpy of small aggregates in the alloyed cluster with decreased size. After about 23 images, corresponding to 1.4×10^9 electrons,

a small dark region starts to form at the lower left of the particle. Subsequently, this region moves to the cluster's lower end where it starts to grow. After 150 images and 9.2×10^9 electrons the particle clearly exhibits a Janus morphology, which does not change significantly during acquisition of the remaining 55 images. Note, however, a thin bright contrast visible at the surface of the Ni region of the particle, indicating the presence of surface Au atoms. This also complies with previous work by Pleth et al. who observed the tendency of Au atoms to bind to low-coordinated atoms at Ni surfaces, forming a surface alloy³². Palomares-Baez et al.³¹ showed theoretically that Au atoms tend to occupy surface sites in Co-Au clusters and predicted a similar behaviour for Ni-Au.

Figure 2b shows that the projected area as well as the measured HAADF intensity vary less than $\pm 10\%$ over the whole image series, hinting at negligible beam-induced mass loss, under the present conditions³³. This also implies that the dose applied to this particular particle per image stays almost constant over the series.

In order to elucidate the kinetics of the segregation process, the experiment was repeated at different temperatures on similarly sized clusters. The graph in Figure 3 shows the number of electrons (deposited on the cluster area until first Ni agglomerations are visible) versus the temperature. We find that the kinetics is a strong function of the temperature. At 400 °C the required dose is almost 20 times higher than at 900 °C. This is an interesting observation because the elastic displacement cross section is only weakly temperature dependent³³⁻³⁵. We also find an exponential relationship which suggests a diffusion-limited process. Presumably, each beam-induced atomic displacement is followed by diffusive relaxation processes, mediating the mass transport in the cluster. We observe the segregation process up to melting of the Au part, despite the increasing entropy contribution to the Gibbs energy with temperature, which in general increases the tendency of alloy formation. Previous studies reported similar processes in Ni-Au thin films, which were irradiated with 1 MeV electrons²³. In this work an increase of the spinodal temperature was found, due to the accumulation of point defects (interstitials and vacancies) in a spatially modulated structure, which contributes to the relaxation of coherent strain. Even though the underlying processes are similar, periodic modulations are not found in our case, most likely because the cluster size is comparable to the expected wavelength of the modulations. Although the clusters do not segregate without the electron beam, the segregated state is highly stable. Once the Janus particles are formed, they do not alloy even at the highest temperatures achievable in our experiments (>950 °C), where Au starts to evaporate from the clusters.

However, alloying of segregated clusters should occur at larger time scales, due to the negative entropy contribution to the Gibbs energy. To test the long-term stability the temperature is kept at 450 °C over 10 hours in microscope vacuum without further electron irradiation. On such large time-scales alloying of the clusters is indeed observed and also the residual Ni core dissolves.

To understand the segregation effect we need to recall how

FIG. 3. Number of applied electrons above which phase separation starts to occur as a function of temperature. The red line shows an exponential fit to the data with parameters given in the inset. Error bars are generated assuming an uncertainty of ± 5 images for the determination of the starting point of segregation. The temperature uncertainty of the heating chips is specified to be less than 5%³⁶.

swift electrons interact with solids. These interactions can in principle be categorized into elastic (electron-nucleus) and inelastic (electron-electron) processes³⁷. In general, both types occur at the same time, and lead to a variety of different damage mechanisms such as radiolysis, defect generation, charging effects, heating, mass loss or chemical reactions^{10,38,39}. The interplay between all these mechanisms is highly complex and difficult to predict. Nevertheless, for reasonably good charge and heat conductors we can reduce most effects to simple knock-on displacements caused by elastic Coulomb interactions of incident electrons with the sample nuclei, under present experimental conditions^{5,33}. Based on these considerations we propose that the phase segregation effect is solely mediated by beam-induced displacements of cluster atoms, which allows us to apply atomistic simulation techniques.

Our simulation approach is based on molecular dynamics (MD) calculations, combined with a Monte-Carlo scheme to account for elastic scattering events. Since diffusive processes are not accessible via MD due to their large time-scale, it is not possible to simulate the full dynamics of the system in this case. We therefore rely on the simulation of an equilibrated, static and alloyed geometry to obtain information about displacement cross sections, dependent on site and species. The algorithm used is described in detail in Ref. 33. In short, for a single scattering event an atom is chosen randomly from an equilibrated cluster during a time-step of a MD run. A scattering angle θ is generated randomly and the velocity vector of the atom is modified accordingly. Since the collision time of an electron with a nucleus is short (in the order of 10^{-21} s) compared with the MD time step, atoms are considered to remain stationary during scattering. After scattering the cluster is equilibrated again, displacements are tracked and the next scattering event is generated with the initial geometry. More details on MD simulations are found in the Supplementary Material.

In contrast to the code presented in a previous publication³³ the present calculations are implemented in Python, which allows to replace the in-house MD core of the code with the more flexible and faster Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS)⁴⁰ using its Python interface (PyLAMMPS).

Despite the high kinetic energy of the electrons the transferred energy during elastic scattering is limited to a few eV, due to energy conservation. The energy E_t transferred by an electron scattered by an angle θ is calculated via

$$E_t = E_{\max} \cdot \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (1)$$

with $E_0 = m_0 c^2$, $E_{\max} = \frac{2E(E + 2E_0)}{mc^2}$

with c the speed of light and m_0 the electron rest mass. Inserting values for electron energy E and atomic masses m in Eq.(1) leads to a maximum transferable energy E_{\max} of 14.5 eV for a Ni atom and 4.3 eV for Au. With knowledge of the differential elastic scattering cross section $\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \Omega}$, found in databases⁴¹, the total cross section for a displacement σ_D event is calculated using Eq. (2)³⁸.

$$\sigma_D = 2\pi \int_0^\pi P(\theta) \cdot \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \Omega} \cdot \sin \theta \cdot d\theta \quad (2)$$

where $P(\theta)$ denotes the probability that an atom is displaced after a certain energy transfer E_t , as a function of θ . $P(\theta)$ is extracted from the simulation data for each individual atom. Figure 4 shows the result of our calculations. The color of each atom in this figure corresponds to the cross section for a displacement event after scattering with this particular atom, obtained via Eq. (2).

The simulation results show that the electron beam preferentially displaces Au atoms, with a displacement cross section which is more than 10 times larger compared to Ni. We also see that σ_D strongly correlates with the coordination number and the local atomic configuration. Surface atoms are likely to be displaced while atoms inside the cluster are less affected by the electron beam, because the maximum transferable energy is too low to cause displacements. Atoms on the top surface of the cluster are also less affected, due to the $\sin^2(\theta/2)$ dependence of E_t (Eq. (1)). The maximum energy E_{\max} is being transferred at $\theta = \pi$ (180°), which corresponds to the central impact case. However, it is important to note that there are also Au atoms inside the cluster, exhibiting relatively large σ_D values. Such atoms are sitting on sites with several Ni neighbors causing local lattice distortions. This lowers their binding energy and consequently they are prone to be displaced. Exemplary, the position of such an atom is marked by a dotted circle in Figure 4.

Accordingly, displacements of Au atoms sitting at less stable sites are the most likely events, leaving vacancies which diffuse towards sinks. Due to the difference in atomic size, the probability that a generated vacancy is subsequently filled by an adjacent Ni atom is larger compared to Au. This process leads to stress relief and Au migration against the vacancy flux^{42,43} and, eventually, to the segregation of Au and

FIG. 4. Simulation results after 10^6 scattering events: Cut through the cluster geometry, comprised of 147 Ni and 353 Au atoms (parallel to x-z-plane), on an amorphous carbon support. Color code corresponds to the displacement cross section σ_D for each atom (Eq. (2)) on a log scale. Ni (a) and Au (b) atoms are imaged separately for better visibility. Insets show the corresponding 3D plot with indicated position of the cut. One Au inside the cluster with a increased σ_D value of 70.8 barn is marked by a dotted circle in (a) and (b). Note that atoms with $\sigma_D = 0$ are also shown in dark colors (10^0) in this graph because a value zero is not depictable in log scale.

Ni. Since the overall shape of the cluster is largely retained, surface diffusion seems to be of less importance for the phase separation, which allows comparison with similar processes observed in the bulk and thin films, irradiated by protons, ions or high-energy electrons^{23,43}.

In summary, we observe the electron beam-induced segregation of alloyed $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Au}_{0.7}$ clusters with *in situ* STEM at temperatures above the miscibility gap ($>400^\circ\text{C}$) of the system. We attribute the observed effects to displacements of cluster atoms by elastic scattering with incident electrons. Our experiments reveal an exponential temperature relationship of the segregation kinetics, which we explain by diffusive relaxation processes which follow beam-induced displacement events. Our observations are supported by atomistic simulations. We believe that the observed effects can be generalized to other forms of irradiation and offer a possible route for the synthesis of non-equilibrated structures.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The Supplemental Material contains supporting EELS data, a Ni-Au phase diagram, details on MD simulation, and an extended discussion based on displacement threshold energies and element specific displacement cross sections.

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